

Information sheet 1.10

Waste management

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment

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A. Description of the RRO

This RRO addresses the management of waste of possibly infested plant material (plant residues, uprooted plants, cut branches...), but also waste associated with the commodity (e.g. used packaging material). It mainly deals with waste in the country of import for a traded commodity or waste resulting from an outbreak.

Proper management of agricultural waste to limit pest prevalence should be part of the good production practices and is not considered in this information sheet. It may be noted that commodities such as "waste wood" are traded internationally but should be considered as a pathway.

When an outbreak occurs, it is crucial to manage properly presumably infested waste (e.g. felled trees) to prevent any further spread and to achieve eradication or containment.

When a commodity is imported, part of the consignment may end up as waste (e.g. fruit/plants not considered suitable for marketing after transport, waste or by-products of vegetables/wood that is processed, used packaging material, waste soil attached to tubers, wash water...). If this kind of waste is likely to be infested by the pest of concern, adequate measures should be applied to mitigate the risk of spread.

Management of waste includes:

- Restriction on the movement of waste,
- Treatment of waste (deep burial, deep burial with quicklime, composting, open air burning, incineration, chipping, production of bio-energy...). Descriptions of the different treatments are available in FERA, 2008.

To ensure that this RRO is effective, it should be applied under official supervision in authorized facilities.

B. Risk factors

The use of the RRO reduces the likelihood of transfer of the pest from waste to a suitable host (plants on the field or healthy consignments) depending on:

- Dispersal mechanisms, including vectors to allow movement from the pathway to a suitable host,
- Risks from by-products and waste,
- Vicinity of suitable hosts to the end-use.

The use of the RRO reduces the probability of spread of the pest acting on the potential for movement with waste material.

Table 1: Points of application of the RROs.

Points where measures may be effective		At place of production (sub-step E1)	In processing facilities before crossing the border of the export country (from sub-step E1 to sub-step E2)	In processing facilities in the risk assessment area (step T)	In processing facilities in the risk assessment area (step S)
RRO	Waste management	X	X	X	X

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

- **Parameters related to the pest or vector**

- Life cycle of the organism: stage likely to be associated with different types of waste (e.g. waste plant material, waste water, waste soil).
- Possibility of survival/reproduction/multiplication in waste (e.g. spore production).
- Spread capacity.

- **Parameters related to the waste**

- Type of waste.
- Some waste plant material can be used further which may create additional risks (e.g. discarded potato tubers may be used for animal feed; waste wood may be processed as wood chips and used as mulch...).

- **Parameters related to the method of waste disposal**

- Efficacy of the waste disposal method to inactivate the pest (burial, composting, steaming, burning, incineration, long storage, etc.). See information sheet 1.14 Heat and cold treatment for these methods. Guidance on composting for plant material is available in EPPO (2005).
- Efficacy of the waste disposal methods to limit spread (e.g. deep burial).
- Possibility to handle large quantity of waste.

- **Others**

- Distances between the place where waste is produced/collected, the designated treatment facility and host plants.
- Tightness of the container used for the transport of the waste to treatment facilities and for storing until processing.
- Timing: proximity of waste and host plants in the sensitive period for contamination.

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

Proper waste disposal is part of good practices in plant production (e.g. EPPO, 2001a; EPPO, 2001b; FERA, 2008). EPPO (2015) provides an extensive review on different kinds of wood waste, their possible uses when traded as commodity and methods that may be implemented for limiting phytosanitary risks associated.

Other regulations (e.g. environmental regulations) may interact with phytosanitary regulations: e.g. in some countries, it may not be possible to have deep burial for plant material, or to dump it on agricultural land. Examples are available in DEFRA (2009).

Depending on the method used and the circumstances (e.g. large outbreak vs. regular production), it may be difficult to handle large quantity of waste in the required time.

Specific facilities or dedicated sites may be required.

Depending on the size of outbreak area, it may not be possible to manage waste within an outbreak area. Risk associated with the transport of waste should also be considered.

For plant material imported for direct consumption via retail market, standards for waste management cannot be controlled other than by making consumers aware of the phytosanitary risk

The cost of treatment may be a limit to the application of this measure.

Some ethical considerations may be raised, for example when large quantity of food has to be destroyed during an outbreak when the pest does not cause human health problems (e.g. potato ring rot).

An example of recommendations on waste management for fruit is available in EFSA (2014).

In EU legislation, requirements for waste management apply for waste produced in delimited zones of the EU territory or for a traded commodity in a Member State or in a Protected Zone of import. Some examples are illustrated below:

- **Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2012/270 on *Epitrix* spp.¹**
Article 3a, Requirements concerning vehicles, packaging, machinery and waste soil. Point 3 on waste soil:
"3. Member States shall ensure that the waste soil, or other waste material, resulting from the fulfilment of the requirements of Article 3(1) and paragraphs 1 and 2 of this Article is disposed of in such a manner to ensure that the specified organisms cannot establish or spread outside a demarcated area."
- **Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2012/535 on *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*²**
Annex I (on eradication measures), point 8:
"...Wood waste produced at the time of felling of susceptible plants which is left on site shall be chipped into pieces of less than 3 cm thickness and width".
- **Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2015/893 on *Anoplophora glabripennis*³**
Annex II, 2. B. (3), requirements related to waste material resulting from the process of specified wood intended for movement:
"...Waste material resulting from the fulfilment of points (1) and (2) shall be disposed of in such a manner to ensure that the specified organism cannot spread outside a demarcated area..."

¹ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2012/270 of 16 May 2012 as regards emergency measures to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the Union of *Epitrix cucumeris* (Harris), *Epitrix similis* (Gentner), *Epitrix subcrinita* (Lec.) and *Epitrix tuberis* (Gentner). OJ L 132, 23.5.2012, p. 18-21. Amended by Commission Implementing Decision 2014/679/EU of 25 September 2014. OJ L 283, 27.9.2014, p. 61-64.

² Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2012/535 of 26 September 2012 on emergency measures to prevent the spread within the Union of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* (Steiner et Buhner) Nickle et al. (the pine wood nematode).

³ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2015/893 of 9 June 2015 as regards measures to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the Union of *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Motschulsky).

- **Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2016/715 of 11 May 2016 on fruits originating in certain third countries infected by *Phyllosticta citricarpa*⁴**

Article 15, Requirements concerning processing of the specified fruits:

"...2. Waste and by-products of the specified fruits shall be used or destroyed in the territory of the Member State where those fruits have been processed in an area where no citrus fruit is produced.

3. The waste and by-products shall be destroyed by deep burial or used by a method approved by the responsible official body of the Member State where the specified fruits have been processed and under the supervision of that official body, in a way to prevent any potential risk for spreading of *Phyllosticta citricarpa*."

The Annex IV, part B of the Council Directive 2000/29/EC⁵ defines provisions for the introduction and the movement of consignments into and within certain protected zones. Points 20.2, 22, 25, 26, 27.1, 27.2 require that processing premises of different plants and plant products of species susceptible to the Beet necrotic yellow vein virus (BNYVV) shall be equipped with officially approved waste disposal facilities in order to ensure the absence of spread of this pest into the protected zone.

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

None.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

This RRO can be the end point of the implementation of other RROs, e.g. RROs described in information sheet 1.05 Cleaning and disinfecting of facilities, tools and machinery and in information sheet 1.08 Physical treatments of consignments or during processing.

Proper waste management is an element of scenarios for eradication and containment. In outbreak situations, this RRO should be applied under official supervision or in certified processing premises to complement the implementation of measures such as cleaning, grading, roguing or pruning.

Requirements on waste management may be associated with the limitation of import of specific commodities only for processing (information sheet 1.18 Post-entry quarantine and other movement restrictions in the importing country; Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2016/715).

⁴ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2016/715 of 11 May 2016 setting out measures in respect of certain fruits originating in certain third countries to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the Union of the harmful organism *Phyllosticta citricarpa* (McAlpine) Van der Aa.

⁵ Council Directive 2000/29/EC of 8 May 2000 on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organism harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community.

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO.

Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	Alternative/ combinations
Pest and vector	At origin	Reduce the probability of entry by reducing inoculum within good production practices	Volumes of waste, availability of facilities, timing.	Cleaning, Physical treatments, Roguing, Pruning, Movement restrictions.
	At destination	Avoid transfer Avoid further spread	Volumes of waste, availability of facilities, timing. To be implemented in authorized facilities	Cleaning, Physical treatments, Roguing, Pruning, Movement restrictions. In EU regulations, often associated with measures aimed to eradication or containment

References

- DEFRA (Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs), 2009. Protecting our Water, Soil and Air. A Code of Good Agricultural Practice for farmers, growers and land managers. TSO, Belfast, Ireland, 118 pp. Available from : <http://adlib.everysite.co.uk/adlib/defra/content.aspx?doc=252412&id=252413>
- EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Plant Health Panel), 2014. Scientific Opinion on the risk of *Phyllosticta citricarpa* (*Guignardia citricarpa*) for the EU territory with identification and evaluation of risk reduction options. EFSA Journal 2014;12(2):3557, 243 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3557.
- EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant protection Organization), 2001a. Guidelines on good plant protection practice. Potato. EPPO/OEPP. PP 2/2 (2), Bulletin OEPP/EPPO Bulletin, 31 : 183-199.
- EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant protection Organization), 2001b. Guidelines on good plant protection practice. Umbelliferous crops. EPPO/OEPP. PP 2/22 (1), Bulletin OEPP/EPPO Bulletin, 31 : 257-287.
- EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant protection Organization), 2005. Guidelines for the management of plant health risks of biowaste of plant origin. EPPO/OEPP, PM 3/66(2), Bulletin OEPP/EPPO Bulletin, 38: 4–9.
- EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant protection Organization), 2015. EPPO Study on wood commodities other than round wood, sawn wood and manufactured items. EPPO/OEPP, Technical Document No. 1071, 38 pp.
- EPPO Standard in development. Management of the phytosanitary risks of soil associated with potato tubers and potato waste.
- FERA (Food and Environment Research Agency), 2008. Code of practice for the management of agricultural and horticultural waste. Available from: <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20140904082245/http://www.fera.defra.gov.uk/plants/publications/documents/copManagementWaste.pdf>